

unavailable. Tillage with cultivators and disk harrows varies from two to five times. We evaluated the cultivator, disk harrow, and rotary puddler for rice cultivation (see table).

Results indicate that

1. It takes more time to puddle with a disk harrow than with a cultivator or rotary puddler, presumably because the harrow has a higher draft requirement.
2. With only one tilling, a rotary blade puddler decreases infiltration rate most to 15 mm/d.
3. A second tilling with a harrow or cultivator further reduces the infiltration rate. One or two tillings with the rotary blade puddler

Performance of various tractor-drawn puddlers in Kaul, India.

	Cultivator		Paddy disk harrow		Rotary blade puddler		CD 5%
	Single operation	Double operation	Single operation	Double operation	Single operation	Double operation	
Puddling time (h/ha)	2.9	4.9	4.0	6.7	3.6	5.8	
Puddling cost (\$/ha)	17	29	24	40	22	35	
Infiltration rate (mm/d)	19	14	15	8	15	15	
Yield (t/ha)	4.2	4.3	3.9	4.5	3.8	3.9	0.075
Hills/m ²	36.8	36	37	36.2	36.2	36.3	
Panicles/hill	8.5	8.2	8.5	8.8	8.2	8.0	
Grains/panicle	110	113	113	125	112	114	8.5
1000-grain mass (g)	28.5	29.6	28.0	28.3	29.7	30.7	1.8

4. Two cultivator tillings produce an infiltration rate similar to that from one tilling with a rotary blade

5. The twice harrow-puddled field had lowest infiltration and yielded most. ∞

Effect of irrigation scheduling and nitrogen application on rice yield

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We studied the effect of four water regimes and three N levels and their interactions on rice yield (see table). The water regimes were imposed during a dry spell in mid-Sep 1984.

Crop water use was 1294 mm (see figure), of which 32% was used in vegetative phase, 45% in reproductive

Weekly rainfall and rate of water use (mm)

Rate of water use at different rice growth stages, Raipur, India.

Effect of irrigation and applied N levels on rice yield, Raipur, India.

Water regime ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)		
	No N	40 kg/ha	80 kg/ha
T1	2.5	3.2	4.2
T2	2.5	3.3	3.7
T3	2.5	3.3	3.9
T4	2.5	3.3	3.8
CD	5%	1%	
N level significance	0.1	0.2	
Water level not significant	—	—	
Interaction significance	0.2	0.3	

^a T1-T4 received 5 cm irrigation water when groundwater level was at the indicated depth (in parentheses).

phase, and 23% during ripening. Rainfall met crop water demand until the vegetative phase. Five cm of irrigation water was applied when the groundwater table receded to 0 (T1), 10 (T2), 20 (T3), or 30 cm (T4). Total water use was 1294 mm at T1, 1110 at T2, 1067 at T3, and 927 mm at T4. Water regime did not significantly affect yield (see table), suggesting that continuous submergence is not necessary to produce high yield and that water use efficiency may be greater with a period of drainage between irrigations.

T1 with 80 kg N/ha produced significantly higher yields than the other treatment combinations, suggesting the need for continuous submergence at higher N application levels for good crop

response to fertilizer. Lack of submergence during reproductive stage reduced the yield benefits under high N application. N level may be important to rice field water management. ∞

Growth depression of blue-green algae (BGA) in lowland fields on the Godavari Delta

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BGA blooms do not develop in Godavari Delta rice fields even with inoculation (algalization). Some possible reasons for failure, obtained mainly from

visual observations, are given here.

Soils usually have medium N fertility (0.75% organic C), low to medium available P (20-50 kg/ha), and high available K (350-500 kg/ha). P encourages BGA blooms, but K does not. BGA blooms disappear immediately after K fertilization.

In summer monsoon, river water is the main source of irrigation. It carries heavy silt deposits into rice fields. Water

turbidity reduces incidental radiation and adversely affects photosynthetic algal activity. Moreover, the silt contains 3 to 5 ppm of K oxide, which may act as a mild algicide.

Close, dry season plant spacing results in a closed crop canopy and hinders penetration of solar radiation into the water. Weeds such as *Marsilea quadrifolia* and *M. minuta* may cover the water surface and further decrease

available light.

Several algal grazers are common. Snails are voracious grazers. Snail infestation is largest the first 2 wk after transplanting, which also is the peak period of BGA bloom development. If field water depth increases, snail population increases. Tilapia, grass carp, catla, and rohu fingerlings abound in rice fields and also feed on algae. *ℳ*

Machinery Development and Testing

A wooden frame for transplanting rice

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Proper plant development occurs only if a crop is well managed from planting to harvest. Management is enhanced with straight rows and evenly spaced hills. We developed an easy-to-handle wooden frame (see figure) to use for line or random transplanting for optimum plant population.

The frame consists of 4, 1-m-long wood strips, 2.5 cm wide and 1 cm thick. All sides have cut markings every 20 cm for 20- × 20 cm spacing. Farmers who

Wooden frame for transplanting rice, Sind, Pakistan.

prefer random planting can transplant 25 plants/ hills. To further facilitate planting, an angle-iron partition in the center can be used to plant 12 hills in one

portion and 13 in another to make 25 hills/m².

The frame has been introduced in farmers' fields. *ℳ*

Announcements

De Datta honored

S. K. De Datta, head of the IRRI Agronomy Department, has received the following awards from the Weed Science Society of the Philippines (WSSP), the Philippine Council for Agriculture Resources Research and Development (PCARRD), the Soil Science Society of America (SSSA), and the American Society of Agronomy (ASA):

- Best Paper Award for a paper titled *Reducing the application volume of 2, 4-D with controlled drop*

applicators in rainfed rice (WSSP),

- Most Outstanding Research and Development Award for the Los Baños Community for a paper titled *Fertilizer application and weed control technology for rice in a resource-scarce Philippine farmers situation* (PCARRD),
- American Fellow Award (SSSA), and
- International Service in Agronomy Award for 1985 (ASA).

De Datta earned his BS degree from Banaras Hindu University and the MS equivalent at the Indian Agricultural Research Institute, both in India, and the PhD at the University of Hawaii, USA. He has been head of the IRRI Agronomy Department since 1967, and

has authored or coauthored more than 200 research and technical papers and three book chapters, and wrote *Principles and practices of rice production*. *ℳ*

Chang lectures published

Six special lectures given by T. T. Chang, head of the IRRI International Rice Germplasm Center, as part of the 1984 Iowa State University Plant Science Lecture Series, Plant Genetic Resources — Key to Future Plant Production, have been published in the Iowa State Journal of Research, Vol. 59, No. 4.

The lectures include Principles of genetic conservation, Collection of crop